

CONTENT AND CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL AND EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN MULTI-SEGMENT SPECIALIZED PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: The purpose of this article is to study and analyze the goals, objectives, principles of education and features of multidisciplinary specialized preschool educational organizations, to study the problems faced by educators in preschool education of children with special educational needs and strategies for overcoming these problems.

Keywords: preschool education, children with special needs, correctional orientation of education; social adaptation, cooperation with educators, cooperation with parents.

Introduction.

The field of preschool education is considered the primary link of the continuous education system, which is of great importance in raising a healthy and well-rounded person in all respects and preparing him for school. Therefore, systematic work is being carried out in our country to further develop this area, to provide education and upbringing not only to healthy but also to children with special educational needs, and to create all the conditions for our children.

Preschool is the period from birth to the time a child starts primary school and plays an important role in children's lives. Because during this period, the child develops mentally, physically, socially and emotionally, acquires language and communication skills, and the child's personality is formed. It is during this period that the child demonstrates a high level of learning potential.

Along with healthy children, preschool education is also very important for children with special needs. Children with special needs differ in their developmental disabilities and abilities, and based on these differences, education is provided to children through classification.

Children with special educational needs are children with individual needs who, regardless of whether they have a disability or not, require special attention from their family, teachers, specialists, society and the state.[3]

The goals of a specialized preschool organization and a combined type of preschool organization are:

- to ensure the child's readiness for education
- to ensure the social adaptation of children and their readiness to continue their education and upbringing;
- to prepare children for study in general education institutions;
- to introduce modern educational programs and technologies into the educational process.[4]

Children with physical or mental disabilities in their development are educated and raised on the basis of the following principles:

- ensuring the implementation of the right to education;
- creating favorable conditions for the education and upbringing of children, their adaptation to society, as well as the correction of developmental defects;
- ensuring their physical, mental and spiritual development in accordance with their age and specific capabilities, abilities and needs;
- ensuring the formation of the child's personality, the development of his creative abilities, and his acquisition of social experience.

The tasks of a specialized preschool organization and a combined type of preschool organization are as follows:

- ensuring the provision of educational and correctional and pedagogical assistance to children in accordance with state requirements for the development of children of early and preschool age, as well as programs for the organization of educational and correctional work developed on their basis;
- to educate children in the spirit of love for the Motherland, respect for the family, respect for national values and traditions, a conscious attitude towards oneself and the environment;
- to conduct medical rehabilitation and rehabilitation, compensation and correction of developmental defects in children;
- to create conditions that allow children to receive quality preschool education and upbringing;
- orientation;
- social adaptation;
- to use a special methodology of education and a categorized approach in organizing the educational process.[4]

Educational services provided to children with special needs, taking into account the individual's specific needs, should be provided by the most qualified, specially trained, specialized teachers.

As a facilitator, the teacher uses his knowledge, skills and resources in the education and upbringing of children. The teacher plans the educational and upbringing process, creates a developmental environment that contributes to the comprehensive development of the child and the disclosure of his potential. [1]

In a specialized preschool organization and a combined type of preschool organization, the educational and upbringing process is organized on the basis of an individual approach, taking into account the specific characteristics of children. Classes are conducted frontally, in small groups and individually[4]

As a result of studying the problems faced by educators in the preschool education of children with special educational needs and analyzing the strategies for solving these problems by educators, it was found that the following problems are encountered when working with children with special needs in multidisciplinary specialized preschool educational organizations:

- problems arising from parents;
- problems arising from the material and technical capabilities of the preschool educational organization;

- problems encountered in the educational process.

The following are indicated as strategies for educators to overcome these problems:

- developing a methodology for effective communication with children;

- developing self-education skills in children;

- correctly distributing time and determining periods of educational activities taking into account the attention of children;

- diversifying activities;

- collaborating with educators;

- creating a methodology for identifying and eliminating the causes of undesirable behavior observed in children;

- independently preparing the necessary materials for activities by the educator based on the needs of the child;

- organizing educational and upbringing activities for the family;

- effectively organizing the child's social adaptation processes.

In conclusion, by increasing the role and responsibility of parents of children with special educational needs in the educational process, conducting events to inform the public about children with special educational needs, offering the services of highly qualified teachers, providing group rooms with the necessary materials according to the needs of children, and creating a methodology for systematically eliminating existing physical and mental disabilities in children, it is possible to eliminate the physical and mental disabilities of children with special needs, develop independent living skills, and provide them with equal opportunities created in society.

References:

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